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Research Article

A Community Based Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Study on Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Jan Aushadhi Kendra (PMBJK)

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ABSTRACT

Background and objective: Rising healthcare costs continue to be a global concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries like India, where a significant portion of the population faces financial hardship due to high medicine expenses. The Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Jan Aushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) was introduced to improve access to affordable generic medicines through government-run Jan Aushadhi Kendras. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) of the community regarding the Jan Aushadhi Scheme and generic medicines in Mangalore. Methodology: A cross-sectional, survey-based study was conducted among 318 community participants between 08/06/2025 and 07/07/2025. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire developed from literature review and translated into English and Kannada. The survey included socio-demographic data and questions categorized into three domains: knowledge, attitude and practice. Descriptive analysis was performed and the results were presented in percentages and tables. Results: Among 318 participants, only 38% were aware of the Jan Aushadhi Scheme and 33% knew about Jan Aushadhi Kendras. Awareness of generic medicines was reported by 35%, while just 30% believed generics are cheaper than branded medicines. Only 25% believed generics were as effective as branded medicines. Attitude was moderately favorable: 34.6% perceived generics to be safe, 37.7% supported training programs for healthcare providers and 40.9% wanted more media coverage. In practice, only 35.8% had visited a Jan Aushadhi Kendra and just 31.1% had purchased generic medicines. Only 23% asked pharmacists and 7.9% requested doctors for generics. Conclusion: The study revealed low levels of awareness and engagement with the Jan Aushadhi Scheme. Misconceptions about safety and efficacy persist, contributing to poor attitudes and limited practices. There is a need for community-based awareness campaigns, training for healthcare providers and policy-level interventions to promote trust and usage of generic medicines in India.

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INTRODUCTION

Increased health-care expenses remain a significant concern worldwide, especially in underdeveloped and developing countries where most people are unable to satisfy them. In step with one among the estimates, 70% of Indian people spend their 10-20% of total income as health expenses finally leading to financial difficulties.¹ A population of around 60% (499-649 million) in India lacks daily accessibility of essential drugs due to increased expenditure on medicines and Essential medicines are inaccessible to 1/3rd population of the world due to high costs.² A generic medicine is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as “a pharmaceutical product, usually intended to be interchangeable with an innovator product that is manufactured without a licence from the innovator company and marketed after the expiry date of the patent or other exclusive rights”.³ A drug product that is comparable to a branded drug product in dosage form, strength, route of administration, quality but different in packing colour and shape.⁴ Generic drugs are lower priced than branded drugs.⁵ Generic medicine cannot be sold at a price higher than the branded medicine.⁶ The Department of Pharmaceuticals, Government of India, introduced the Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) or Jan Aushadhi scheme in 2008 in response to the financial burden that marketed branded drugs and there are 9998 Janaushadhi Kendras functional across the country. Their product list comprises 1800 drugs and 285 surgical items.⁷ In September 2015, the "Jan Aushadhi Scheme" became the "Pradhan Mantri Jan Aushadhi Yojana" (PMJAY) and in November 2016 relaunched as the "Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana" (PMBJP).⁸ Here the costs of scheduled and non-scheduled drugs are regulated by the National

Pharmaceutical Pricing Authority under the Government of India.⁹

The purpose of the study is to analyze the knowledge, attitude and practices of the community regarding the Jan Aushadhi scheme.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design:

A survey was conducted with the help of questionnaire to collect the data from the community to assess their knowledge, attitude and Practice towards Jan Aushadi Scheme at Dakshina Kannada (Mangalore). Articles were collected from the online sources such as PUBMED and GOOGLE SCHOLAR and questionnaire were prepared by using these articles. The data obtained from this survey were analysed, assessed and interpreted.

Study site: The present study was survey-based study which were conducted among the community in Dakshina Kannada(Manglore).

Study duration: The study was enrolled people during the time schedule (from 08/06/2025 to 07/07/2025).

Sample size: The sample size were 318.

Study criteria:

Inclusion criteria: Individuals willing to participate and voluntarily enrolled were included for the study.

Exclusion criteria: Subjects less than 18 years of age and not willing to participate were excluded from the study.

Study Data collection: Data was collected through surveys using structured questionnaires adapted from previous studies [10] and modified to suit our purpose. Questionnaire were prepared

in English and Kannada including all relevant variables based on the objectives of study.

The tools used have 4 sections designed to address:

1. Socio-demographics characteristics
2. Knowledge
3. Attitude
4. Practice of participants towards Jan Aushadi Scheme

Data analysis: Sample characteristics were computed in percentage/suitable and it is presented using tables and figures.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Demographic details

Category	Subgroup	N	%
Gender	Male	185	58.0 %
	Female	133	42.0 %
Age Group	18–25	63	19.8 %
	25–40	64	20.1 %
	40–50	111	34.9 %
	Above 50	80	25.2 %
Monthly Income	< ₹25,000	175	55.0 %
	₹25k–₹50k	95	29.9 %
	₹50k–₹75k	32	10.1 %
	₹75k–₹1 Lakh	13	4.1 %
	> ₹1 Lakh	3	0.9 %

Occupation	Homemaker	80	25.2 %
	Head-load worker	64	20.1 %
	Self-employed	57	17.9 %
	Government worker	38	12.0 %
	Corporate employee	38	12.0 %
	Student	25	7.9 %
	Other	16	5.0 %

In this study 318 participants were surveyed, among them 185 were men (58%) and 133 were women (42%). The age profile is quite mature. About 35% are between 40 and 50, another 25% are over 50 and the rest are younger 20% in the 25 to 40 age group and 18% in the 18 to 25 group. Regarding salary of participants, most people fall into the lower income range. Around 55% earn under ₹25,000, another 30% make between ₹25,000 and ₹50,000 and only a small number earn over ₹50,000. Specifically, 10% earn between ₹50,000 and ₹75,000, 4% earn between ₹75,000 and ₹1 Lakh and just 1% make above ₹1 Lakh. Finally, looking at the job types of these individuals, 25% are homemakers, 20% work as head-load laborers, 18% are self-employed and 12% each work in government or corporate jobs. We also have 8% who are students and 5% in various other roles.

Fig 1: Demographic Details

Fig 2: Age Group

Table 2: Knowledge of Patients About Jan Aushadhi Kendras and Generic Medicines

Sl no	Question	Yes N (%)	No N (%)	Not sure N (%)
1	Are you aware of PMBJP (Jan Aushadhi scheme)?	121 (38.0 %)	197 (62.0 %)	—
2	Are you aware of Jan Aushadhi Kendra?	105 (33.0 %)	213 (67.0 %)	—
3	Have you heard of generic medicines?	110 (34.6 %)	208 (65.4 %)	—
4	Do you think generics are cheaper than branded?	96 (30.2 %)	177 (55.7 %)	45 (14.1 %)
5	Do you know the difference between branded & generic medicines?	110 (34.6 %)	208 (65.4 %)	—
6	Are you aware of government regulations on these medicines?	76 (23.9 %)	165 (51.9 %)	77 (24.2 %)
7	Do you know generics are as effective as branded medicines?	80 (25.2 %)	238 (74.8 %)	—

Out of the 318 participants, only 38% (121) aware about PMBJP (Jan Aushadhi Scheme), while 62% (197) did not. Awareness dropped slightly for the Jan Aushadhi Kendras, with just 33% (105) saying yes and 67% (213) responding no. Awareness of generic medicines was even lower only 35% (110) had heard of them, while 65% (208) had not heard about generic medicines. Regarding price perception, only 30% (96) believed generic drugs are cheaper than branded one s, while 56% (177) disagreed and 14% (45) were not sure. About 65%

(208) not knew the difference between branded and generic medicines, only 35% of participants (110 out of 318) knew the difference. Most of the participants 52% (165) were unaware about government regulations governing generic and branded drugs followed 24% (77) were not sure, Only 24% (76) said they were aware. Only few of them 25% (80) believed generics are as effective as branded medicines, compared to 75% (238) who did not knew it. This highlights that there is a significant lack of knowledge, most participants

are unaware, unsure about Jan Aushadhi Kendra Scheme.

Fig 3: Knowledge of patients about Jan Aushadhi Kendras and generic medicines

Table 3: Attitude of patients about Jan Aushadhi Kendras

Sl no	Question	Yes N (%)	No N (%)
1	Do you think generic drugs are safe?	110 (34.6%)	208 (65.4%)
2	Do you think there is a need for training programs for healthcare providers on generics?	120 (37.7%)	198 (62.3%)
3	Should the government implement stricter laws for the Jan Aushadhi scheme?	95 (29.9%)	223 (70.1%)
4	Would you like to know more about the Jan Aushadhi scheme through media?	130 (40.9%)	188 (59.1%)
5	Did you find the medicines at Jan Aushadhi Kendras equally effective?	105 (33.0%)	213 (67.0%)

Only 110 participants (34.6%) believed that generic drugs are safe, while 208 (65.4%) did not.

Approximately 120 respondents (37.7%) felt there is a need for training programs for healthcare providers on generics, compared to 198 (62.3%) who disagreed. Just 95 participants (29.9%) supported stricter government laws for the Jan Aushadhi scheme, whereas 223 (70.1%) opposed the idea. Interest in media coverage was somewhat higher, with 130 individuals (40.9%) wanting to learn more through newspapers, television or online platforms and 188 (59.1%) saying they would not. Finally, only 105 participants (33.0%) felt the medicines available at Jan Aushadhi Kendras were equally effective, while 213 (67.0%) disagreed about effectiveness. These results show that less than half of respondents hold a favorable attitude toward the safety, regulation, promotion and perceived efficacy of generic medicines and the Jan Aushadhi scheme. The majority remain not sure and not interested the need for comprehensive educational efforts targeting both healthcare providers and the general public.

Fig 4: Attitude of patients about Jan Aushadhi Kendras

Table 4: Perception of patients about Jan Aushadhi Kendras

Sl no	Question	Yes N (%)	No N (%)
1	Have you ever visited any Jan Aushadhi Kendra?	114 (35.8%)	204 (64.2%)
2	Have you ever purchased generic medicines?	99 (31.1%)	219 (68.9%)
3	Have you ever requested a pharmacist to dispense generic medicines?	73 (23.0%)	245 (77.0%)
4	Have you ever requested your doctor to prescribe generic medicines?	25 (7.9%)	293 (92.1%)

Only 114 participants (35.8%) have visited a Jan Aushadhi Kendra, while 204 (64.2%) have not. And 99 respondents (31.1%) have bought generic medicines, but the majority 219 (68.9%) have not bought generic medicines. Only 23% (73 out of 318) of respondents actively asked a pharmacist for generic medicines, whereas the majority 77% (245) did not and a very small proportion 7.9% (25) ever asked their doctor to prescribe generics, while 92.1% (293) never approached doctor. Most participants had only limited interaction with generics just 1/3rd visited a Jan Aushadhi Kendra and purchased generic medicines. Fewer still asked a pharmacist for generics and almost none had requested their doctor to prescribe them. Practice also found to be less.

Fig 5: Perception of patients about Jan Aushadhi Kendras

DISCUSSION:

Knowledge

The present study highlights a significant gap in public knowledge regarding the Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Jan Aushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) and generic medicines. Only 38% of participants were aware of the PMBJP and even fewer (33%) knew about the Jan Aushadhi Kendras. These results are comparable to the findings by Leonora et al., who reported that only 33.1% of patients understood that generic drugs were compositionally similar to branded drugs [11]. In our study, awareness of generic medicines found to be 35%, which is near to the results of Nabil et al., who noted that 71.7% of their participants had never heard of generics and 32% even perceived them as harmful [12]. In terms of understanding drug pricing and efficacy, only 30% of our participants believed that generics are cheaper than branded drugs, while the majority either disagreed or were unsure. This is similar to the findings of Claudio et al., who identified a noticeable gap in public understanding regarding the pricing and quality of generic medicines [13]. Furthermore, knowledge about drug regulation

was also poor in our study, with only 24% aware of the governing rules. This gap is consistent with the study by Himmel et al., where older, less educated and chronically ill patients often perceived generics as inferior due to their lower cost [14].

Attitude

The attitude of the public toward generic medicines and the Jan Aushadhi Scheme was unsatisfied. Only 25% believed that generics are as effective as branded drugs and just 34.6% considered them to be safe. Furthermore, only 33% felt that medicines from Jan Aushadhi Kendras were equally effective. These attitudes are shaped by poor knowledge and mistrust, similar to the national survey by William et al., where only 37.6% agreed to use generics and 53.7% reported that their prescribers did not discuss drug types with them [15]. Although a small proportion (37.7%) supported the idea of training programs for healthcare providers, and 40.9% showed interest in learning more through media platforms, the overall attitude remained unfavorable. This supports earlier findings by Manisha et al., who found that 10% of patients

considered generic drugs to be harmful [16]. In contrast, a more favorable outlook was observed in the study by Kishor, et al., where 60.86% of patients knew that generic drugs were equally effective as branded ones [17]. This disparity may be due to differences in education levels and socioeconomic backgrounds of the study populations.

Practice

Practice patterns in this study revealed limited real-world engagement with the Jan Aushadhi Scheme and generic medicines. Only 35.8% had visited a Jan Aushadhi Kendra and just 31.1% had ever bought a generic drug. Active involvement, such as asking a pharmacist (23%) or requesting a doctor (7.9%) for generics, was very low. These figures illustrate a disconnect between awareness and action and align with the current literature that highlights low public engagement with generic substitution even when awareness exists [12,14]. The limited practice may be due to a lack of trust, insufficient education, or poor communication from healthcare providers, as seen in similar studies globally. Moreover, the resistance to stricter laws (only 29.9% in favour) for promoting generics shows Uncertainty toward regulatory enforcement, echoing findings by William et al., where a majority felt prescribers did not adequately communicate about generics [15].

CONCLUSION:

The study reflected that awareness about the Jan Aushadhi scheme and generic medicines is generally low among participants. Many respondents lacked knowledge of key information such as government regulations, cost-effectiveness and therapeutic equivalence of generics. Attitudes toward safety and effectiveness were also not optimal, with limited support for policy implementation and training initiatives. In

practice, most participants had minimal interest with Jan Aushadhi Kendras or generic medicine usage. Very few actively requested generics from healthcare professionals. Overall, the outcome suggests the need for targeted awareness campaigns and educational interventions to improve understanding and acceptance of generic medicines among the community.

Future prospectives:

- Enhance awareness through community-based campaigns(Hospital etc.) and digital media(Advertisement in TVs, radio, social medias etc.)
- Promote education about generic medicines in health programs and school/college.
- Train healthcare providers (doctors/pharmacists) to recommend generic medicines.
- Strengthen public trust by ensuring consistent quality and availability at Jan Aushadhi Kendras.
- Conduct future research to explore barriers from both consumer and provider perspectives.
- Evaluate long-term impact of PMBJP on healthcare affordability and access.
- Establish feedback systems for continuous improvement of Jan Aushadhi services.

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